

1 **Ribosome subunit composition in metastasis to the lymph nodes in humans with breast cancer.**

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7 We report here specific ribosome subunit composition in lymph node metastasis in human breast cancer.
8 Genes up-regulated during transition from primary tumor to lymph node metastasis included Rps8, Rpl22,
9 Rpl10l, Rpl38, Rps12, Rps14 and a ribosomal RNA RRP1B. Targeted ribosomal interference may present
10 some level of adjunctive or secondary clinical efficacy in humans with solid tumors, particularly those with
11 metastasis or treatment resistant disease.

12 Citations

13 1. Ruggiero D, Pandolfi PP. Does the ribosome translate cancer? Nat Rev Cancer. 2003
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